

A Randomised Control Study to compare the hemodynamic stress responses during laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation using Coopdech® VLP-100 Videolaryngoscope as compared to Macintosh laryngoscope

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Abstract

The Coopdech® Video Laryngoscope VLP-100™ (CVL) is a digital intubation tool that allows direct visualization of the vocal cords during intubation. Laryngoscopy and intubation results in increased hemodynamic responses in patients. This prospective, randomized control study was conducted to evaluate and compare the hemodynamic responses during laryngoscopy and intubation with the CVL and Macintosh laryngoscopes in patients without comorbidities. A total of 140 patients were equally and randomly divided into two groups and the mean heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and mean arterial pressure were compared at baseline, after induction, before laryngoscopy, and at different points of time after intubation. The results showed a significant rise in all parameters at 1 minute and 3 minutes after intubation in both groups ($p < .05$), but no significant difference in parameters between the two groups ($p > .05$). The time taken to intubate was significantly more with the Coopdech Videolaryngoscope than with the Macintosh laryngoscope. The study concluded that the Coopdech videolaryngoscope did not show any advantage over the Macintosh laryngoscope in terms of attenuating hemodynamic responses following laryngoscopy and orotracheal intubation.

Keywords: Macintosh, Videolaryngoscope, Haemodynamic Response, Intubation Time.

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Introduction

Anaesthesia today is safer than it has ever been due to advances in pharmacology, technology and more stringent practice standards and yet difficult endotracheal intubation is still a significant adverse event and requires specific learning [1]. Although the American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) has come up with algorithms to identify and avoid difficult airway situations, it is still a dreaded complication in anaesthesia practice [2]. The design of laryngoscopes and the procedure of endotracheal intubation have recently undergone a radical change due to the advancement of more affordable, compact, and dependable video cameras. Videolaryngoscopes include a wide variety of instruments that perform endotracheal intubation by using a video camera instead of line-of-sight viewing [3]. One such instrument is the Coopdech® Video Laryngoscope VLP-100™ (CVL) by DAIKEN MEDICAL.

Laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation can cause sympathetic activation and adverse physiological effects, especially on the cardiovascular system, resulting in arrhythmia,

tachycardia, or hypertension [4,5]. In susceptible people, this may be harmful, leading to increased morbidity and mortality [6]. The degree of oropharyngeal and laryngeal structural manipulation may be related to the magnitude of the hemodynamic responses during tracheal intubation and laryngoscopy [7].

While some literature suggests that hemodynamic responses are better maintained with various videolaryngoscopes when compared to Macintosh laryngoscopes (MAC) [8-10], there are studies which found no significant difference [11-14]. The Coopdech® Video Laryngoscope VLP-100™ (CVL) allows a direct visualization of the vocal cords on a digital screen during intubation [15]. No study was found comparing Coopdech® to other intubation tools for hemodynamic responses.

The aim of this study was, primarily, to evaluate and compare the hemodynamic responses during laryngoscopy and intubation with the CVL and Macintosh laryngoscopes in otherwise healthy adult individuals receiving general anaesthesia for elective surgeries. We also compared the time to

intubation in these laryngoscopes in patients facing no difficulties in intubation.

Materials and Methods

The present prospective clinical trial was carried out following approval of the study protocol on the 12th of August 2015 by the Institutional Ethics Committee, Gauhati Medical College & Hospital. The study was carried out under the Department of Anaesthesia and Critical Care in Gauhati Medical College & Hospital in a period of one year from September 2015 to September 2016. At the time of starting this study, any other study reporting the hemodynamic parameters using the traditional modifications type of videolaryngoscope could not be accessed.

Therefore, taking into account the data reported by Pournajafian AR et al [13], a sample size of 60 per group was found to be required to detect a difference of 10 mm of Hg Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) or 8 beats per minute difference of Heart Rate (HR) with a power of 80% and significance level of 0.05. Considering a dropout of 10%, it was decided that 140 patients would be taken for study allotted into two groups.

The study population was selected from among the patients scheduled for elective surgery under general anaesthesia. The patients were randomly and equally divided into two groups, Group A and Group B using a computer-generated random number table, each group containing of 70 patients.

Inclusion Criteria

- Informed consent for inclusion in the study
- 18 – 60 years old patients of either sex.
- American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status class I and II.
- Mallampati grades (MPG) I and II.
- Patients posted for elective surgery under General Anesthesia and requiring endotracheal intubation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Hypertension, lung disease, cardiovascular disease, cervical spine disease, gastro-esophageal reflux disease
- Anticipated difficult intubation
- Allergy to the used anesthetic medications
- O₂ saturation \leq 94% during ventilation or intubation
- Difficulty with mask ventilation during anesthesia,
- Intubation failure (>1 attempts)
- Intubation time > 30s with Macintosh laryngoscope
- Need for another person to complete the procedure.

After taking informed consent, 140 patients meeting the above-mentioned inclusion criteria were randomly but equally allocated to one of the two groups, Group A and Group B with the help of a predetermined random number table. This random number table was computer generated with the help of the website www.random.org. Each group consisted of 70 patients.

Following induction, all patients received anaesthesia in accordance with a predefined departmental protocol. The patients in Group A were intubated using a conventional Macintosh laryngoscope (Mac) while the patients in Group B were intubated using COOPDECH® video laryngoscope portable VLP-100 (CVL).

Study Design: Prospective randomized control study.

Preoperative Preparation: The patients were visited in the ward for pre-anesthetic check up in the evening before surgery. A detailed history was taken and clinical examination done. Modified Mallampati score was recorded while the patient was sitting with mouth open and tongue protruded. Thyromental distance was measured as the distance between the anterior chin and the thyroid notch while the patient's neck was fully extended. All the patients were also asked to bite their upper lip and upper lip bite test (ULBT) was performed.

ASA physical status was assessed and the patients meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were allotted to either Group A or Group B. This allocation was done according to a predetermined computer-generated random number table as mentioned earlier. The patients were explained about the study and the instruments we proposed to use for endotracheal intubation and proper informed consent was taken. Each patient received Tab Alprazolam 0.5 mg and intravenous antibiotic on the night before surgery. The patients were asked to have light diet on the night before and to stay nil per orally from 10PM of the night before surgery.

On the morning of surgery, after putting an intravenous line, using an appropriate cuff size, the blood pressure of each patient was measured with the same calibrated and checked indirect non-invasive arterial pressure machine. Intra-operative monitoring included pulse oximetry, electrocardiogram, and non-invasive arterial pressure. The Heart rate (HR), Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP), Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP), Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) and SPO₂ (peripheral arterial oxygen saturation) were recorded. These pre-induction hemodynamic parameters were taken to be the baseline parameters. Before the start of the general anaesthetic procedure, all patients received an intravenous standardized premedication of Inj.

Fentanyl 2mcg/Kg and Inj Lignocaine (2%) 1.5 mg/Kg. All the patients were preoxygenated with 100% oxygen through a face mask for three minutes, and then general anesthesia was induced with intravenous administration of Inj. Propofol 2-3 mg/Kg till a loss of verbal contact to the patient was established. Inj. Vecuronium 0.1mg/kg administered intravenously thereafter. The patients were then ventilated for the next three minutes. As neuromuscular monitoring was not available in our institution, laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation was done in all patients after three minutes of administration of the intravenous dose of vecuronium. Systolic BP, diastolic BP, mean arterial pressure (MAP), and heart rate (HR) were recorded at numerous intervals as follows: baseline, after induction of anesthesia, just before laryngoscopy, one, three, five and ten minutes after intubation and fixation of endotracheal tube. The laryngoscopic visual grading of the patients was noted using Cormack & Lehane grading.

During intubation, no change in the electrocardiogram was noticed in any of the patients. Two patients in Group A (Mac) and six patients in Group B (CVL) were excluded from the study at this stage as each of them required a second attempt. One more patient got excluded in Group A as the SPO₂ fell below 94% during intubation (the patient was managed well thereafter as SPO₂ returned to 100% after intubation on positive pressure ventilation with 100% O₂).

A second person (a single operating room technician) acted as the timekeeper using a digital stopwatch. Total intubation time (in seconds) was defined as the time from insertion of the assigned intubating device into the mouth up to the time the endotracheal position of the tracheal tube was confirmed by five-point auscultation and cuff was inflated. Another patient in Group A had to be excluded at this stage as time taken for intubation

exceeded 30 seconds. Polyvinyl chloride Murphy-type cuffed tracheal tubes with an internal diameter of 7.0 to 8.0 mm were used for all the patients. After intubation, the patients were maintained on positive pressure ventilation with a tidal volume of 8-10 ml/Kg and plane of anaesthesia was maintained with O₂:N₂O = 1:2 and isoflurane (0.6-1% dial setting). All laryngoscopy and intubation procedures were performed by a single investigator (a second-year anesthesiology resident with about 2 years' experience in using Macintosh laryngoscopy). Prior to starting the study, the investigator had no previous experience of intubation using video laryngoscope. The investigator performed 20 successful intubations with GVL under supervision of a senior attending anesthesiologist at our hospital. After these first 20 cases that were not included in our study, the competency of investigator was approved to independently perform intubations using a video laryngoscope.

Insertion Technique

The COOPDECH® video laryngoscope (CVL) unit is used in the same manner as an ordinary laryngoscope, with the exception that the blade is introduced in the midline or slightly to the left, using a gentle curving action until the glottis is identified. There is usually no need for any lifting force. In the CVL group (group B), an intubating stylet was adequately lubricated with a silicone-based fluid and inserted into the tracheal tube. The distal end of a styletted tracheal tube was lubricated and bent anteriorly in the shape of a hockey stick to an angle which corresponded to the COOPDECH® video laryngoscope (CVL) blade curvature. Attention was paid to insert and remove laryngoscopes smoothly and not to damage the oral cavity, tongue, or patient's dentition.

Results and Discussion

CONSORT Flow Diagram showing the Study Design of the study

At the end of the study, the collected data was analyzed by appropriate statistical methods. Tests employed were paired and unpaired t-test, Fisher's exact test and Chi-square test as applicable. The software used was Graphpad InStat version 3.0. Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel were used to generate graphs and tables. P value > 0.05 was

considered not significant while that < 0.05 was considered significant.

As evident from Table 1, the demographic characteristics (age, weight, height, BMI, sex distribution and ASA grading) of Group A and Group B are comparable. There is also no significant difference in the airway characteristics of both the groups, as shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Table showing distribution and central tendency of the demographic characteristics in the two groups

	Group A, n=66	Group B, n=64	P value
Age (Mean ± SD) (Years)	38.11 ± 10.300	37.69 ± 11.900	0.8308
Weight (Mean ± SD) (Kg)	53.82 ± 9.340	53.91 ± 10.135	0.9590
Height (Mean ± SD) (cm)	158.20 ± 9.936	157.41 ± 10.453	0.6594
BMI (Mean ± SD) (Kg/m ²)	21.43 ± 2.666	21.70 ± 3.109	0.6061
Sex- M/F (n)	20/46	15/49	0.4319
ASA- I/II (grade)	57/9	59/5	0.3978

n- Number of patients, SD – Standard Deviation

Table 2: Table showing distribution and central tendency of the airway characteristics in the two groups

	Group A, n=66	Group B, n=64	P value
MPG- I/II (grade) (n)	45/21	45/19	0.8505
ULBT- I/II (class) (n)	59/7	56/8	0.7890
TMD (Mean ± SD) (cm)	7.015 ± 0.3315	7.034 ± 0.3301	0.7410

n- Number of patients, MPG—Mallampati Grade, ULBT – Upper Lip Bite Test,

SD – Standard Deviation, TMD—Thyromental distance

The mean heart rate (HR), Systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) of Group A and Group B were compared at baseline (before induction), after

induction, before laryngoscopy, at 1 minute, 3 minutes, 5 minutes, and 10 minutes after intubation.

Table 3: Mean Heart Rate at different predefined points of time

Heart Rate (beats per minute)	Within Group		Inter Group		
	Group A	Group B	Group A	Group B	
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	P Value [^]	P Value [^]	P Value [#]
Baseline	78.73 ± 13.577	79.27 ± 11.438			0.8065
After Induction	77.29 ± 12.579	78.77 +/- 9.536	0.5222	0.4768	0.4503
Before laryngoscopy	77.32 ± 12.250	78.67 +/- 9.679	0.5205	0.6674	0.4863
1min after intubation	83.55 ± 14.695	83.39 +/- 12.001	0.0371*	0.0031*	0.9458
3min after intubation	83.77 ± 13.056	84.23 +/- 10.813	0.0055*	0.0003*	0.8270
5min after intubation	77.11 ± 9.520	77.81 +/- 11.876	0.3245	0.4704	0.7119
10min after intubation	78.08 ± 10.271	78.11 ± 9.813	0.7042	0.5256	0.9864

Table 4: Mean SBP at different predefined points of time

SBP	Group A		Group B		Within Group		Inter Group P Value [#]
	Mean ± SD	SD	Mean ± SD	SD	P Value [^]	P Value [^]	
Baseline	121.32 ± 11.757		123.38 ± 11.088				0.3059
After Induction	118.18 ± 10.12		122.59 ± 10.453		0.0618	0.5726	0.0159*
Before laryngoscopy	118.02 ± 10.912		123.98 ± 11.126		0.1025	0.7558	0.0025*
1min after intubation	127.95 ± 13.145		129.05 ± 11.978		0.0005*	0.0093*	0.6187
3min after intubation	126.95 ± 11.540		130.77 ± 10.826		0.0014*	0.0003*	0.0537
5min after intubation	121.62 ± 10.349		121.95 ± 10.768		0.8667	0.5797	0.8590
10min after intubation	120.29 ± 9.400		123.25 ± 10.033		0.5704	0.9477	0.0852

Table 5: Mean DBP at different predefined points of time

DBP	Group A		Group B		Within Group		Inter Group P Value [#]
	Mean ± SD	SD	Mean ± SD	SD	P Value [^]	P Value [^]	
Baseline	73.39 ± 9.255		73.16 ± 9.272				0.9860
After Induction	71.44 ± 8.518		70.98 ± 11.908		0.1309	0.2272	0.9750
Before laryngoscopy	72.10 ± 8.327		72.89 ± 8.980		0.4016	0.8403	0.9487
1min after intubation	78.11 ± 10.806		78.27 ± 12.356		0.0016*	0.0065*	0.9922
3min after intubation	77.11 ± 9.255		78.58 ± 11.969		0.0150*	0.0061*	0.9228
5min after intubation	72.82 ± 8.858		72.70 ± 7.289		0.7142	0.7533	0.9917
10min after intubation	72.14 ± 9.857		72.20 ± 7.589		0.4692	0.5594	0.9962

Table 6: Mean MAP at different predefined points of time

MAP	Group A		Group B		Within Group		Inter Group P Value [#]
	Mean ± SD	SD	Mean ± SD	SD	P Value [^]	P Value [^]	
Baseline	88.17 ± 10.090		89.58 ± 9.338				0.4106
After Induction	85.96 ± 8.619		88.16 ± 10.419		0.1050	0.4119	0.1928
Before laryngoscopy	86.21 ± 8.607		89.17 ± 8.642		0.2416	0.7953	0.526
1min after intubation	94.17 ± 11.721		95.20 ± 15.732		0.0003*	0.0057*	0.6736
3min after intubation	93.79 ± 10.704		95.98 ± 11.253		0.0004*	0.0009*	0.2580
5min after intubation	88.56 ± 9.117		89.25 ± 8.103		0.8078	0.8290	0.6489
10min after intubation	88.15 ± 9.315		89.20 ± 7.994		0.9925	0.7956	0.4912

SBP– Systolic Blood Pressure, DBP – Diastolic Blood Pressure, MAP – Mean Arterial Pressure.

SD = Standard deviation,

[^] p value in each group when mean Heart Rate at different points of time is compared to that at baseline.

[#] p value when mean heart rates are compared between the groups at different points of time

* p < 0.05

From Tables 3 to 6, it can be seen that the mean HR, SBP, DBP and MAP decreased after induction and increased after intubation in both the groups but the decrease in these values after induction and

before laryngoscopy were not found to be statistically significant in any of the groups (p > 0.05). Again, the mean values of these vitals at 1 minute and 3 minutes after intubation in both

groups were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the mean baseline values of each group (Tables 3-6). The mean HR, SBP, DBP and hence the MAP declined again at 5 and 10 minutes after intubation in both the groups and they reached values which were not significantly different from the mean baseline heart values in each group ($p > 0.05$).

The mean HR, SBP, DBP and MAP at different points of time were found to be comparable in both the groups. No statistically significant difference was seen between the means of the two groups at any point of time.

Fig 1. Bar diagrams showing Mean HR, MAP, SBP and DBP at different predefined points of time

Table 7: Table showing the time mean time for laryngoscopy and intubation

	T _{mean} (Mean ± SD) (seconds)	P value
Group A	15.21 ± 3.270	< 0.0001
Group B	30.48 ± 6.139	

T_{mean} – Mean time taken for laryngoscopy and intubation (seconds)

Fig 2. A Bar diagram showing mean time for intubation in the two group

The mean time taken for laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation in Group A was found to be 15.21 +/- 3.270 sec while that for Group B was found to be 30.48 +/- 6.139 sec. The difference in intubation time was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

A thorough search of all the studies available was made but no study was found comparing the hemodynamic responses during laryngoscopy and intubation with the COOPDECH® video laryngoscope portable VLP-100 to the responses with any other type of laryngoscope. But there have been some studies comparing these responses among some other similar types of videolaryngoscopes.

Bilehjani et al performed a study to compare the hemodynamic response to laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation with the GlideScope® videolaryngoscope to that with the Macintosh laryngoscope in patients with ischemic heart disease. Changes in hemodynamics following the induction of anesthesia and at 1, 5, and 15 minutes showed no significant differences between the two scopes [11].

In another study involving patients scheduled for elective coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG), the haemodynamic changes and time required for endotracheal intubation were compared between conventional laryngoscopy and video laryngoscopy using the Pentax AWS. Both groups experienced a drop in arterial pressure after the induction of anesthesia but before laryngoscopy, which was attributed to the hemodynamic effects of anesthetic induction and the loss of consciousness. There were no notable differences between the groups in terms of SBP, MAP, and DBP; however, within each group, SBP, MAP, and DBP showed a significant decrease during the 5-minute observation period. Also, the difference in the duration of endotracheal intubation was found to be statistically significant [12].

A randomised control study involving the Glidescope and the Macintosh laryngoscope found that following intubation, arterial pressure rose markedly in both groups, peaking at 1 minute after the procedure, where it was substantially higher than the pre-laryngoscopy measurements in both groups. Nonetheless, there were no considerable differences in hemodynamic responses observed between the two groups at any time point. The duration of the intubation process was notably longer for the GlideScope compared to the Macintosh group [13].

In another study with three blades, viz. the Macintosh, the McGrath and the Trueview, it was found that video laryngoscopes did not show any benefit regarding hemodynamic response in patients with a normal airway undergoing CABG

compared to Macintosh laryngoscopes. Time to intubate was also significantly less with the Macintosh laryngoscope as compared to the other two video laryngoscopes [14].

These studies, therefore, show similar results to our study in which the hemodynamic response is subdued after induction and before laryngoscopy, but they increase after intubation and are at their maximum at one to three minutes after intubation. But there is no significant difference seen between the Macintosh laryngoscope and COOPDECH® video laryngoscope portable VLP-100 on the hemodynamic changes occurring after laryngoscopy and intubation.

Limitations

1. This study was conducted on normal patients, and hence, results cannot be extrapolated to patients with hypertension, anticipated difficult orotracheal intubation or having other comorbidities.
2. It is impossible to blind the investigator or observer to the device being applied, which prevents double blinded trial from being performed and resulting in potential for bias.
3. Ideally invasive BP monitoring would have been more informative to capture more frequent BP readings.

Conclusions

In patients that were presumed to have normal airways, the Coopdech® video laryngoscope VLP-100 did not show any special advantages over the Macintosh laryngoscope in terms of the attenuation of hemodynamic changes following orotracheal intubation. The intubation time in the Coopdech® group was significantly longer as compared to the Macintosh group. However, if the time taken for intubation with the Coopdech® video laryngoscope could somehow be decreased, then probably the advantages of the laryngoscope over the Macintosh may be demonstrated in terms of decreased hemodynamic responses.

There is further scope for studies to evaluate the cause of this difference of hemodynamic responses with the various types of video laryngoscopes.

List of Abbreviations

ASA - American Society of Anaesthesiologists
CABG - Coronary artery bypass grafting
CVL - COOPDECH® video laryngoscope
DBP - Diastolic Blood Pressure
MAC - Macintosh laryngoscopes
MAP - Mean Arterial Pressure
MPG - Mallampati Grade
SBP - Systolic Blood Pressure
SD - Standard Deviation
TMD - Thyromental distance

ULBT - Upper Lip Bite Test

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The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows:

Study conception and design: FAT, PK

Data collection: BT

Analysis and interpretation of results: VB, PK, BT

Draft manuscript preparation: FAT, VB

All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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